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Review Article

**REVIEW STUDY: MANAGEMENT OF TRIGEMINAL
NEURALGIA****Hanan Obaidallah Al harbi¹, Ibrahim Abdulrahman Bakhsh², Mishal Abdullah Alghamdi²,
Mahmoud Mohammad Shawly², Mohamad Abdulrahman Bakhsh³, Sami Samran Alrehaily⁴**¹ Consultant Family Physician, Public Health Administration² Alfarabi College - Jeddah³ GP in king abdulaziz Hospital .⁴ GP In Hera Hospital**Abstract:**

Trigeminal neuralgia (TN) is one-sided confusion portrayed by brief electric stun like pain. The management is confusing as numerous patients will get medical surgery after the failure of their medicinal treatment, while others require therapeutic treatment after the long-haul viability of medical surgery gradually weakens. This literature review was established to review the available medications and their safety and effect on quality of life. In conclusion, there's still a debate regarding the treatment of TN as yet it's challenging as individual's reactions to various remedial alternatives may differ extensively. Just a couple of accessible treatment alternatives have affirmed viability satisfying current norms for proof-based drug. Although, novel medical alternatives are on the ascent just because substances are in clinical testing on more numbers of patients specially for this exceptionally impairing yet uncommon disease. Result's indicators and hazard factors for medical management failure are more methodically evaluated to an increasing extent with the goal that an individual patient-guided medication choice can be made. The constant exertion by clinicians, scientists, and the pharmaceutical business may give helpful choices that are progressively specific, tolerable and increasingly proficient for subjects diagnosed with TN.

Keywords: Trigeminal neuralgia (TN),management, carbamazoid, surgery

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INTRODUCTION:

Trigeminal neuralgia (TN) or the tic douloureux. In the 21st century drug, the pathophysiology of TN was built up through a more profound comprehension of the physiology and improvement of imaging methods. Because of its rambling nature, its underlying management and diagnosis fall under the consideration of the general professional practitioners (GPs)(1).

According to the International Headache Society, Trigeminal neuralgia (TN) is characterized as a "one-sided confusion portrayed by brief electric stun like agonies, abrupt and sudden during the beginning and end, and constrained to the dispersion of at least one divisions of the trigeminal nerve"(2). The International Classification of Headache Disorders, third release, beta adaptation (ICHD-III) orders TN as exemplary (basic or idiopathic) TN without or with corresponding facial agony and persistent pain(2, 3). TN after injury, tumor, herpes zoster, or numerous sclerosis is delegated into secondary aching trigeminal neuropathy. A slight hyperesthesia or hypoesthesiais currently in accordance with the diagnosis of the classic type of TN(4).

TN normally begins in the second or third division of the trigeminal nerve(3). An inclusion of the ophthalmic nerve might be related with other differential findings including the serious one-sided neuralgiform cerebral pain assaults with conjunctival infusion and tearingand fortunately is prevalent in lower than 5% of cases(5). Commonplace TN assaults typically last between 1 second and a couple of moments. TN may likewise happen in groups of various term and force enduring as long as 2 minutes. The assault is trailed by a short recalcitrant period in numerous patients, during which another assault can't be evoked by further incitement (6). In the middle of eruptions and at the end the patients are typically recovered; nonetheless, in certain patients, the endurable episodes may persist(3).

There is a lack of pathophysiological systems clarifying this corresponding ache, yet it is by all accounts related with a poor restorative and surgical consequences and outcomes. However numerous patients react to first-line treatment at first, most medication methodologies will in general lose viability after some time, so new and imaginative treatment choices are justified. Numerous patients will get medical surgery after the failure of their medicinal treatment, while others require therapeutic treatment after the long haul viability of medical

surgery gradually weakens(7, 8).

Incidence and prevalence:

A study in the United Kingdom conducted by general practitioners during the period between 1992 to 2002revealed the occurrence of TN is 26 patients for every 100,000 every year(9). The National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke appraises the rate pace of 0.012% for every year(10). There is sexual orientation in the frequency of TN with a female to male proportion of 1.74:1 with the vast majority of the cases happening following 50 years old (11).

Presentation

Practically 87% of every facial agony are associated with dental or oral mucosal injuries(12). Important factors should be considered for correct diagnosis of TN including clinical history, assessment, examinations, and imaging (13). TN is described by a sudden beginning and fleeting one-sided stun like torment, constrained to the circulation of the trigeminal nerve. The most common triggers for classic TN (CTN) type are rumination, contact, and tooth brushing followed by eating, talking, and cold breeze on the face. Brushing hair isn't typically a typical trigger for TN. There can be attendant foundation of pain inside the dissemination of the nerve. Pain is normally circulated along the V2 and V3 branches. Pain happens marginally more regularly on the right side of the head and two-sided pain is very rare. TN is sub-classified into classical, secondary, and idiopathic causes(4).

Etiology and pathophysiology

Many studies lead to the vascular-pressure hypothesis of CTNdemonstrating that TN is brought about by the weight of veins on the trigeminal nerve as it leaves the brain stem. Most usually, a rostroventral superior cerebellar artery circle packs the trigeminal nerve and results in the side effects (14).

Prognostic factors

CTN is a clinical finding dependent on the historical backdrop of the patient and an exhaustive physical test, especially a neurological test. Imaging (MRI/MRA) is frequently used to affirm the analysis and to prohibit other potential reasons for facial agony. Imaging procedures can help find the territory of the neurovascular circle just as locate any optional causes. Neurophysiological account of trigeminal brainstem reflexes and trigeminal evoked possibilities help recognize the injury (4). Therapeutic treatment for the vast majority of patients with TN is essential. Therapeutic treatment gives help from unbearable

torment and lessen the recurrence and length of pain.

A proper diagnosis is the vital factor for satisfactory treatment and along these lines a decent result. Differential diagnosis of trigeminal autonomic cephalalgias and other craniofacial torment disorders or relentless idiopathic facial agony is very essential for unique and proper treatment(15, 16).

Established medical treatment

Table 1.

First line	Second line	Surgery	Alternative medicines
Carbamazepine (600–1200 mg/day)	Lamotrigine (400 mg/day)	Percutaneous procedures on the Gasserian ganglion	Pregabalin (150–600 mg/day)
Oxcarbazepine (600–1800 mg/day)	Baclofen (40–80 mg/day)	Percutaneous glycerol rhizolysis	Topiramate (100–400 mg/day)
	Pimozide (4–12 mg/day)	Radiofrequency thermocoagulation	Gabapentin (900–3600 mg/day)
		Balloon compression	Valproate (600–2400 mg/day)
		Gamma knife radiosurgery	Tocainide(20 mg/day)
		Microvascular decompression	

Alternative medical treatment options (class III or IV)

- Pregabalin (150–600 mg/day)
- Gabapentin (900–3600 mg/day)
- Topiramate (100–400 mg/day)
- Tocainide (20 mg/day)
- Valproate (600–2400 mg/day)

First-line treatment

The first line of treatment should be Carbamazepine with a dose ranged from 200 to 1,200 mg/day. On the other hand, oxcarbazepine 600–1,800 mg/day can be utilized, as proposed by current treatment guidelines(18). There is a proof for the safety of carbamazepine, however the wellbeing profile of oxcarbazepine is better when compared to carbamazepine(19, 20).

The pain-relieving activity and mode of action undoubtedly identifies with blocking of the voltage-

There're various choices that generally utilized for treatment of TN but the efficiency differs according to the patient's response. Medicinal treatment ought to be the primary decision, and simply after two bombed treatment endeavors, surgical intercessions may be considered. About 33% to half percent of patients may require careful surgical mediation eventually(17). The established TN treatments are presented in table 1.

sensitive sodium channels that prompts adjustment of membranes of the hyperexcited cells, decrease of proliferation of synaptic impulses, or potentially hindrance of repetitive terminating(21). A little dose is required during the early treatment of TN to be compelling, and significantly lower than what might be needed for the epilepsy treatment. Once in a while the pain reacts to 100 mg for 3 or even two times a day. A dose of 300–800 mg per day partitioned into 2 or 3 doses per day dosages is viewed as powerful. Around 80% of patients advantage at first, however increased doses are frequently required after some time to maintain viability. The carbamazepine autoinduction of carbamazepine prompts a decrease

in viability among half of patients(22).

Common side effects include queasiness, tiredness, hyponatremia, diplopia, unsteadiness, ataxia, and rise of transaminases. Unfavorably susceptible rash, myelosuppression, hepatotoxicity, lymphadenopathy, fundamental lupus erythematosus, Stevens–Johnson disorder, and aplastic sickliness are conceivably genuine yet unprecedented reactions. The US Food and Drug Administration prescribes hereditary evaluation for Asian patients since they are hereditarily more susceptible forevolving Stevens–Johnson disorder. Serum sodium levels, tests of the liver function, and a total blood count are required after 2 months of treatment to distinguish complexities at an early stage. Oxcarbazepine is an analogue for carbamazepine which is quickly changed into the pharmacologically dynamic 10-monohydroxy metabolite. The drug metabolite has just a little impact on hepatic catalyst enzyme and therefore has a significantly better reaction profile. Oxcarbazepine is an option to carbamazepine and is typically begun at 150 mg two times per day, and expanded by 300 mg at regular intervals until relief from discomfort is accomplished without side effects. The required maintenance dose is 300–600 mg twice every day (20, 23).

Second-line treatment

There is restricted proof supporting second-line treatment proposals. The normally utilized medicines are baclofen 40–80 mg/day, lamotrigine with a dosage of 400 mg per day, or pimozide with a dosage of 4 to 12 mg per day(24). The drug that has the long term side effects is Pimozide including extrapyramidal side effects so is occasionally utilized in clinical practice. Baclofen is a GABAB receptor agonist that diminishes the excitatory neurotransmission. Twofold blinded investigations have shown its adequacy among up to 70% of patients at dosages of 10–60 mg per day(25). The common symptoms are tiredness, stupor, gastrointestinal inconvenience, and dazedness. Baclofen has the second-best logical proof supporting its viability after carbamazepine(26).

Lamotrigine can block the sensitive sodium channels, represses the arrival of impulse synapses, and balances out the membranes of the neurons. Lamotrigine indicated superior prevalence for TN treatment among patients obstinate to carbamazepine(27, 28). The beginning dose is 25 mg/day, and ought to be expanded gradually to 200–400 mg per day. Reactions to lamotrigine incorporate queasiness, wooziness, ataxia, and obscured vision.

The rashes of the skin can happen among 7%–10% of patients inside the initial two months of treatment(29). Desquamation and extreme rash related with side effects of lymphadenopathy and fever are indications of Stevens–Johnson disorder, which necessitates fast termination of the medication. These reactions are less inclined to happen when the titration is done gradually. Unlikely, numerous patients can't endure moderate and careful titration due to pain(30).

Alternative treatment options

Many antiepileptic medications were researched in many studies including valproate, topiramate, phenytoin, pregabalin, gabapentin, and levetiracetam, tocainide and clonazepam that have demonstrated some beneficial medications(31, 32).31 Newer antiepileptic medications are encouraging for future examination because they often have less medication drug interaction and less serious symptoms. The occurrence of TN increments with age, thus age-related physiological changes which may modify pharmacokinetics including diminished renal and hepatic capacity, lower expected medication protein-binding, diminished blood stream, and connections with medications utilized for concomitant disorder treatment will turn out to be increasingly more important for patient security and treatment adequacy(33, 34). The drug can't be endured among 6-10% of patients.

Gabapentin is begun at 300 mg for each day and can be expanded gradually by 300 mg for 2–3 days whenever endured. Moderately minor symptoms and the absence of medication interactions are the principle highlights of gabapentin. Side effects incorporate sleepiness, unsteadiness, loose bowels, cerebral pain, queasiness, perplexity, and lower leg growing(35).

Topiramate demonstrated viability at a dosage of 100–400 mg/day among 75% a small sample of patients(36, 37). Levetiracetam was evaluated in a prospective study during a period of 10-week time frame which revealed that 40-90% of patients were improved after using a dose of 4,000 mg per day(38, 39). These fundamental discoveries should be affirmed by randomized controlled preliminaries later on.

Tizanidine is a midway acting alpha-adrenergic agonist that indicated viability among 80% of patients with TN. But after the follow up for 1–3

months, all patients experienced repeat of pain(40).

Neuralgia is frequently treated with phenytoin, which has demonstrated to be powerful in a small uncontrolled examination. the relief of pain was accomplished by an intravenous portion of 14 mg/kg, which lasted for 1–2 days. This is roughly the time span during which oral drugs begin working(41). Lidocaine 8% directed as a nasal splash additionally accomplished impermanent alleviation of neuropathic pain(42).

Sumatriptan 3 mg regulated subcutaneously accomplished checked absence of pain in 80% of patients with generally stubborn TN. The length of relief from pain was 8 hours(43, 44). An elective treatment strategy is using local narcotic for the superior cervical ganglion among patients with neuropathic facial agony. More than half percent of the patients reported pain reveal with the first treatment(45, 46).

Neuromodulation techniques

Neuromodulation provides an elective value suggested for patients suffering from neuropathy pain which is obstinate to medical treatment. The accessible neuromodulation includes Central and peripheral types however the clinical proof base is exceptionally constrained for these techniques. Choices incorporate stimulation of the electrical Gasserian ganglion, peripheral nerve, intrusive engine cortex and non-obtrusive cortex(47-49).

Repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS) is likewise a generally novel innovation presenting the plausibility of testing the patient's response with trigeminal neuropathic torment to intrusive epidural cortical stimulation. An original research conducted among 48 patients showed that 24 patients with TN were treated with every day 20-Hz motor cortex incitement through the span of five days. Evaluations of pain diminished by 45% for 2 weeks minimally (50). An alternate examination included 12 patients who failed to undergo medical procedure with unmanageable TN, more than half of the patients revealed over 30% decrease of pain force following rTMS(51) and recent studies also declared closed results (52-54).

Surgical treatment

Patients undergoing therapeutic treatment with at least two proper dosed TN recommended drugs together with CBZ are possibly candidates for surgical management. The patients' presentation, indications, and no neuroimaging examinations are the most

important factor for this choice(55, 56). Careful TN surgical administration is ablative with the deliberate obliteration of tangible capacity of the trigeminal nerve or non-destructive with negligible decompression of the trigeminal nerve and protection of its ordinary normal function and capacity(57).

The treatments for Gasserian ganglion are considered medium term minor technique with exceptionally low mortality levels (18, 19). The procedures to the Gasserian ganglion are ruinous for most of the parts and comprise essentially of percutaneous glycerol rhizolysis, radiofrequency thermocoagulation, and inflatable pressure. Relief of the pain was accounted by 90% of TN patients experiencing these techniques. Around 68 to 85% of patients remain torment free following 1 year yet this falls apart to 54 to 64% following 3 years and just half are still free from pain following 5 years. The loss of sensation is the most widely recognized symptom with high side effect on quality of life and personal satisfaction for these patients(58, 59). Dysesthesias (6%) is the most common side effect that occurs after sensory loss followed by corneal numbness with danger of keratitis among 4%, and anesthesia dolorosa (4%)(60).

Gamma blade surgery is a medical procedure that utilizes an engaged radiation bar to cut off the trigeminal root located in the posterior fossa. About 695 of patients were accounted to remain free from pain for 1 year after gamma blade surgery without extra drugs or medicaments. The ratio is decreased to 52% after 3 years. Pain relief medications may be required for 1 month after the surgery. Tangible difficulties of the senses were accounted among 6% of patients with a postponement of half year, incorporating paraesthesias among 6 to 13% of patients, and facial numbness among 10 to 37% that may improve with time(18, 19). The quality of life and personal satisfaction improves by 88%(58, 59). Although, gamma blade medical procedure is very costly which constrains increasingly board utilization. Thus this surgery is held only for patients unfit to hold up under ordinary medical procedure or with blood coagulation sickness or prescription(61, 62).

As for microvascular decompression surgery, the most supported pain reliever was accounted following microvascular decompression medical procedure. About 90% of patients had starting relief from discomfort. Over 80% were still pain free 1 year after medical procedure and this ration is tumbled to 75% following 3 years and 73% for the following 5

years(60). Microvascular decompression surgery is a significant careful procedure incorporating craniotomy to access the trigeminal nerve located at the posterior fossa. Death rates ranged between 0.2 to 0.5% and reached to 4% of patients who are critically ill with serious side effects including hematomas, infarcts, or cerebrospinal liquid spillage. The most common complications after the surgery are aseptic meningitis, followed by hearing misfortune and sensory loss (18, 19).

The recent examinations concentrated on the long periods assessment of various careful surgeries and medicines (63)(64)and the development of basic careful surgical procedures(65, 66). An enormous number of studies were led recently, however the vast majority of them stay on a distinct level unfit to reveal proof-based examinations and accordingly motivate just indirect suggestions and recommendations. The timing and correct plan for the surgery are still a debate (67). Thus it is just reasonable to refer patients who are non-responsive to drug medications to undergo surgery without delay (68, 69).

CONCLUSIONS:

There's still a debate regarding the treatment of TN as yet it's challenging as individual's reactions to various remedial alternatives may differ extensively. Just a couple of accessible treatment alternatives have affirmed viability satisfying current norms for proof-based drug. Although, novel medical alternatives are on the ascent just because substances are in clinical testing on more numbers of patients specially for this exceptionally impairing yet uncommon disease. Result's indicators and hazard factors for medical management failure are more methodically evaluated to an increasing extent with the goal that an individual patient-guided medication choice can be made. The constant exertion by clinicians, scientists, and the pharmaceutical business may give helpful choices that are progressively specific, tolerable and increasingly proficient for subjects diagnosed with TN.

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